

FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AS KEY FACTORS IN PREPARING YOUNG PEOPLE FOR MODERN PROFESSIONS

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Abstract. *This article highlights the importance of foreign languages and digital technologies in preparing young people for modern professions. Nowadays, due to increased international cooperation and competition in the labor market, learning foreign languages for young people is becoming increasingly important. At the same time, mastering digital technologies is an integral part of modern professions and is a key tool in forming the professional competence of young people. The article emphasizes the relevance of innovative approaches, modern pedagogical technologies and the formation of practical skills in the educational process. It also reveals the strategic importance of foreign languages and IT skills in adapting young people to the global labor market.*

Аннотация. *В данной статье подчеркивается важность иностранных языков и цифровых технологий в подготовке молодежи к современным профессиям. В настоящее время, в связи с усилением международного сотрудничества и конкуренции на рынке труда, изучение иностранных языков для молодежи приобретает все большее значение. В то же время, освоение цифровых технологий является неотъемлемой частью современных профессий и ключевым инструментом формирования профессиональной компетентности молодежи. В статье подчеркивается актуальность инновационных подходов, современных педагогических технологий и формирования практических навыков в образовательном процессе. Также раскрывается стратегическая важность иностранных языков и ИТ-навыков в адаптации молодежи к глобальному рынку труда.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqolamda yoshlarni zamonaviy kasblarga tayyorlashda xorijiy til va raqamli texnologiyalarning ahamiyati yoritiladi. Hozirga kunda xalqaro hamkorlik va mehnat bozoridagi raqobatning kuchayishi tufayli yoshlarning xorijiy tillarni o'rganish muhim ahamiyatga ega bo'lib bormoqda. Shu bilan birga, raqamli texnologiyalarni egallash zamonaviy kasblarning ajralmas qismi bo'lib, yoshlarning kasbiy kompetensiyasini shakllantirishda asosiy vosita hisoblanadi. Maqolada ta'lim jarayonida innovatsion yondashuvlar, zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar va amaliy ko'nikmalarni shakllantirishning dolzarbligi ta'kidlangan. Shuningdek, u yoshlarni jahon mehnat bozoriga moslashtirishda chet tillari va IT ko'nikmalarining strategik ahamiyatini ochib beradi.*

Keywords: *digital technologies, profession, labor market, education, competence, skills, IT.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровые технологии, профессия, рынок труда, образование, компетенция, навыки, информационные технологии.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli taxnologiyalar, kasb, mehnat bozori, ta'lim, kompetensiya, ko'nikma, IT.*

Introduction. Today, our lives are changing very rapidly. Technologies are developing, new professions are emerging, and old professions are being updated based on the requirements of the times. In such conditions, the issue of preparing young people for future professions is becoming more important than ever. Now it is not enough to have only theoretical knowledge. A modern specialist must be comprehensively developed, flexible and open to innovations.

The labor market is currently becoming increasingly competitive. Employers are paying attention not only to a diploma, but also to practical skills, the ability to think independently and knowledge of modern technologies. Especially since digital technologies have become an integral part of our daily lives, many professions are directly related to computers, the Internet and various programs. Areas such as programming, graphic design, Internet marketing, artificial intelligence, online shopping are opening up great opportunities for today's youth.

At the same time, the process of globalization has further strengthened ties between countries of the world. Now it is possible to live in one country and work remotely with a company in another. To effectively use such opportunities, it is necessary to know foreign languages. In particular, English occupies a special place as a means of international communication. A young person who knows a foreign language can study foreign experience, participate in international projects, and further enrich his knowledge.

The education system is not left out of these changes. Modern pedagogical technologies, digital platforms, and interactive methods are widely used in schools and higher education institutions. Because today's youth are tomorrow's specialists. It is an important task to educate them as modern, competitive, and independent-thinking individuals.

Therefore, in-depth teaching of foreign languages and digital technologies is of particular importance in preparing young people for modern professions. This serves not only their professional development, but also their personal growth and broadening of their worldview.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-187 dated April 28, 2022, "On Accelerating Digital Transformation in Education" provides for the widespread introduction of digital technologies in the education system, improving the quality of education, and providing students with the opportunity to learn through modern digital means is an important document on the creation of. The resolution includes issues of creating a new digital infrastructure in the education system, providing teachers with modern technologies, and the effective use of digital resources at all stages of education. The modern education system is taking shape today in a global digital environment. The rapid development of information and communication technologies, the widespread use of artificial intelligence, digital platforms, online learning systems, and multimedia tools - all this creates the need to introduce new approaches to pedagogical activities. Taking into account the needs of the new generation of students for rapid assimilation of information, flexible thinking, and independent learning, the process of digitizing education is becoming increasingly relevant. The integration of digital technologies into the educational process is one of the main directions of modern pedagogy, and this process is carried out based on deep theoretical foundations. In particular, based on the constructivist approach, knowledge is formed depending on the student's activity, through his experience and the process of perception. According to this theory, the learner is not a passive recipient of information, but a subject who independently constructs knowledge. Digital technologies act as a tool in this process. For example, interactive simulations, virtual laboratories, educational applications and digital constructors allow the learner to actively assimilate information, experiment, analyze the results and form his own point of view. Digital technologies are becoming not only a tool in education,

but also an active participant in the learning process. This requires new methods and innovative ideas in pedagogical approaches." (Z. Ergashev, Digital Transformation in Education: Opportunities and Challenges. Tashkent: Uzbekistan Pedagogical Publishing House. (2022).)

At the same time, "A new stage, a new era has begun in the teaching of foreign languages in our country. The use of advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, and communicative and information tools is required in the process of teaching a foreign language. In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) for teaching a foreign language and assessing the knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. Textbooks have been created for vocational students in accordance with these requirements. In accordance with these requirements, schools have been equipped with new information and communication technologies: computers, televisions, and the Internet. "The desire of students to learn a foreign language is increasing day by day," Isroilova Okilahon Abdurasulovna emphasizes in her article (<https://newjournal.org/01/article/view/13546/13147>)

The globalization process has strengthened economic, political and cultural ties between countries of the world. Remote work opportunities have expanded, the number of international companies has increased. Now it is possible to live in one country and cooperate with an organization in another.

To effectively use such opportunities, it is necessary to know foreign languages. In particular, English occupies a special place as a means of international communication. Most scientific articles, technological innovations, international grants and educational programs are presented in English.

The modern education system is also not left out of global changes. Digital platforms, online courses, interactive methods are widely used in schools and higher education institutions. Virtual laboratories, educational applications and multimedia tools make the learning process more effective and interesting.

Digital technologies in the educational process:

- develop independent learning skills;
- help to quickly and effectively assimilate information;
- form creative and critical thinking;
- expand the possibilities of distance learning.

In addition, interactive methods and innovative approaches transform the learner into an active participant, rather than a passive listener. This is consistent with the principles of the constructivist approach, which means that knowledge is formed through the active participation of the learner.

In the process of preparing young people for modern professions, it is advisable to pay attention to the following areas:

- In-depth and practically oriented teaching of foreign languages.
- Formation of digital literacy starting from the school stage.
- Increasing practical training in IT and innovative technologies.
- Strengthening the integration of education and production.
- Effective use of distance and blended learning opportunities.

These factors serve not only the professional, but also the personal development of young people.

Today's world is completely different from yesterday. New technologies are emerging every day, professions are being updated, and some professions are even disappearing altogether. In such conditions, preparing young people for their future life is not a simple matter. Now it is not enough to just get a diploma - it is very important to be able to apply knowledge in practice, understand technologies, and communicate freely in foreign languages.

Many professions are related to computers and the Internet. Areas such as programming, graphic design, internet marketing or artificial intelligence are creating great opportunities for young people. And digital skills are necessary to succeed in such areas.

In addition, the world is getting closer. Now it is possible to live in one country and work for a company in another. But for this, knowledge of a foreign language is a must. Especially English has become a means of international communication today. A young person who knows a language has wider opportunities, he learns foreign experience and is not limited in working on himself.

The article also mentions the reforms being implemented in the education system. Digital platforms, interactive methods, modern technologies are being widely introduced in schools and universities. This encourages students to think independently, research and strive for innovation.

In short, foreign languages and digital technologies are of decisive importance in the process of preparing young people for modern professions. In order to become competitive specialists in the digital economy, young people need to master modern technologies and be able to communicate freely in foreign languages.

Today's youth are tomorrow's leading specialists. One of the main tasks of the education system is to educate them as individuals who are adapted to the global labor market, have modern competencies, and think innovatively. Only then will our country's development and competitiveness in the international arena be ensured.

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